

AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH ON MODULAR JOINTS FOR CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

Within the EU-Project MOdular JOints a material driven design for aeronautics composite components based on T-, L-, H- and Pi-shaped joints was developed. This paper is focusing on the manufacturing steps for the Pi-shaped joints, including the preforming, the out-of-autoclave infusion and the pressure free bonding process.

Keywords: CFRP, resin infiltration, VARI, preform, adhesive bonding, out-of autoclave infusion

INTRODUCTION

Composites are associated with integration, complexity, manufacturing risk, weight savings and high costs. The main goal of MOJO is to reduce the risks and use the potentials of composite design. Cost savings are achieved with out-of autoclave infusion processes and tailored preforms made of high performance textiles. Adhesive bonding, as the most compatible joining method for composite parts, provides also significant cost and weight savings. The challenge is to create synergy between preform infusion and adhesive bonding processes. In this respect, MOJO is representing a boltless differential structural design as a modular approach. Simplified structural elements are subsequently inserted into the joints and bonded using adhesives. The manufacturing risk is reduced through decreased integration of a differential design. Therefore a demonstration structure, a generic flap track, was chosen to show the potentials of this design. This flap track (figure 1) exists of 2 side panels, 2 upper panels and a lower panel. These panels are connected by bonded modular joints. Here the manufacturing cycle of the lower panel is described which is a flat panel with two integrated parallel Pi-joints.

Figure 1: The target structure with the highlighted Pi-section discussed here

PREFORMING FOR COMPLEX SHAPES WITH Z-REINFORCEMENT

The first major step to guarantee a satisfactory part with low manufacturing risk and cost savings is the preforming step. Here a binder fixed ready to use preform was developed to produce the complex shaped Pi-preforms.

The preforming manufacturing process is starting up with the preparation of 4 different sub-preforms. Several NCF-strips varying in size are put over each other. After that the single NCF-layers of the sub-preforms are compacted and fixed with heat and pressure in plane shape by using a vacuum preform table (figure 2).

Figure 2: Preform Table (left) and 4 compacted sub-preforms (right)

In the next step the sub-preforms positioned on the bottom plate accordingly to the lay-up (figure 3 left). The U-layers and the L-layers were folded and clamped before. Two braided gusset fillers are placed along the corners between them.

Figure 3: Preforming: Lay-up of the Pi (left), heating (middle), demolding (right)

The process ends up with the consolidation (melting of binder) of the folded sub-preforms with heat under vacuum using the preform table with infrared heaters (figure 3 middle). The temperature is set at 120-140°C for 15 minutes at a pressure of 10 mbar to consolidate the NCF layers. After cooling down the 3D-shaped pi-preform is demolded (figure 3 right). In figure 4 the final Pi-joint preform is shown.

Figure 4: 3D-Shaped Pi-Preform Top and Bottom View

Additional different 3D reinforcements (Z-reinforcement) were tested to optimize the strength of the connection between the panel layers and the Pi-joints. These reinforcements were a tufted and a velcro like one.

Figure 5: Tufting Process of Pi-Test Specimens

The tufting was done with an untwisted HM-carbon yarn M50-1000-50A from Toray. The seam parameters were set at a stitch length of 3 mm with 13 seams in parallel. The tufting process starts with the fixation of the Pi-preform on a flat table jig with 3 EPP foam stripes. One is put into the flange gap of the preform. The other two stripes are placed along the flange foot. Everything is turned upside down and clamped on the jig

(figure 5 left). After that the skin layers are put on top and fixed to avoid a shifting of the NCF skin layers during the tufting process. Accordingly the tufting robot is stitching the defined seam pattern (figure 5 right).

The second Z-reinforcement method which was developed is the use of Velcro Pin Stripes (VPS). The VPS consists of several rows of micro carbon fiber rods which are positioned and fixed by a thin layer of carbon fibre laminate. This is made out of one layer carbon plain weave with 120g/m² and two layers of 300g/m² adhesive film. The first VPS samples, which were manufactured by hand, had shown that the principle and function of Z-reinforcement with VPS is basically working. In order to make the process more sufficient and productive an automated production process was developed to produce a larger quantity of VPS material with a higher accuracy and quality. On this account a pinning machine from the company Autosplice, which assembled electronic cards with metal pins, was modified and adapted to work with endless micro carbon rods. A detailed picture of a VPS is shown in figure 6 right.

The assembly of the Pi-preforms with Velcro Pin Stripes is starting with the positioning of the VPS on top of the skin layers. After that the Pi-preform is set beyond and holds in position with the metal Pi-preform tooling. Accordingly the carbon pins are pushed into the NCF-layers of the skin and the Pi with 1 bar pressure using a vacuum table. Additionally the preform is heated up to 120°C for 15 minutes to melt the binder fleece in the Pi in order to ease the penetration of the pins into the NCF-layers. At least the joined Pi is cooled down for release.

Figure 6: Schematic Construction of pinned Pi-Preform (left); Velcro Pin Stripe (right)

INFILTRATION WITH INNOVATIVE TOOLING CONCEPT

To infiltrate the Pi-section the Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion process (VARI) and pi-preforms with tufted Z-reinforcement was used. The VARI process was developed by the Institute of Structures and Design of the German Aerospace Center (DLR) [1] and is similar to the EADS Premium Aerotec developed process called VAP [2] Both processes allow cost effective resin infusion of different reinforcing textiles with all demands required by the aircraft industries. Meanwhile both processes have been demonstrating their usability for serial production.

The goal in development of both processes was to provide a low cost process which enables the industry to manufacture high performance composite aircraft structures having fiber volume fractions up to 60%. Therefore, low tooling and labor cost had to be achieved. Additionally, expensive process equipment like autoclaves or heated press should be avoided, which leads to a vacuum assisted process. The usage of dry fabrics

and liquid resins in an infusion process also reduces the material cost compared to prepreg materials. The basic principal of the process is impregnation of the fabric in thickness direction, which is realized by a particular resin distribution fabric on top of the dry lay-up. Figure 7 shows the principal lay-up for the VARI-process. The lay-up is almost similar to a conventional vacuum bagging except the resin distributing fabric. The main difference between the VARI and the VAP process is the use of a semi-permeable membrane to ensure low porosity and high process stability.

Figure 7: Schematic layup of the VARI process

Unfortunately both processes ensure only one side with an exact shape: the side which is defined by the mould. The other side is defined by the thickness of the used fabric and the vacuum pressure. If a defined surface is needed on both sides additional tooling is needed. In the case of the Pi-section a flat lower side and exact positioned bonding gaps on the opposite side are needed. Therefore an innovative tooling concept had to be developed which was driven by two main requirements. First there were small tolerances at the bonding gap of the Pi to guarantee a reproducible and qualitative bonding. The second main requirement was that the outer contour (e.g. the laminate thickness) of the Pi differs depending on the used Z-reinforcement. Therefore an outer tooling was developed composed out of a rigid steel core and a flexible contour tool made out of CF-PEEK (Figure 8 right). The rigid steel core guarantee an exact positioning of the outer contour and the flexible part adjust the laminate thickness and provides a smooth transition to the area were the contour is defined by the vacuum bag. The exact geometry and position of the gap was ensured by massive T made out of steel including the resin inlet. The T is about 1400mm in length and is supported and positioned at both ends.

Figure 8: Tooling concept and infiltrated cross section of Pi-profile

After the tooling and the infiltration concept was proven in several infiltrations, producing excellent Pi-sections which fulfil all requirements, it was extended for the infiltration of two parallel Pi-joints (figure 9).

Figure 9: Infiltration setup before apply of the vacuum bag

Figure 10: Infiltrated and milled lower panel with the two Pi-joints

In figure 10 the infiltrated and milled lower panel can be seen. Also two holes were cut out, which are needed to assemble the target structure (figure 1). The next step was to join the lower panel with the upper part of the target structure by bonding.

BONDING AS A COST-EFFICIENT JOINING METHOD

The final product on both aeronautical and automotive industry consists of multiple component parts and/or structures joined together. Adhesive bonding is one of the most efficient methods to joint these parts. Bonding is also the solution for applications where weight are critical, but demand strength and durability. Epoxy based films are state of the art for bonding composite parts/ structures. Two component paste adhesives made of epoxy based are nowadays applied as gap fillers and as semi-structural assembly adhesive. This last allow reducing costs in structural joining where riveting, in lower amount, is simultaneously used. Novel paste adhesives development has the objective to be ready to do the further step and find place for structural applications.

Paste adhesive was chosen for the work described in this paper due to its flexibility for tolerances, to its suitability for complex geometries and its advantage regarding automatic application. Assembly using adhesive bonding shall behave process robustness, less cycle times and less cost than riveting or other joining techniques. The maximal efficiency is reached with fully automation of the process not only the

adhesive application itself but also all steps which will assure the quality of the adhesive bonded structure. That means, from the capture of geometries for the structural detail and the insert, the treatment of the surface and its control, the adhesive application and also its control, the curing of the adhesive, and of course the control of the cured joint. This paper deals only with the application concept and quality control of the cured joints (without kissing bonds).

A tooling concept was developed to joint, using paste adhesive, the insert plates and the side panels with the Pi-sections in a semi-automatic way (figure 11). First, paste adhesive are mixed and placed in the bottom of the Pi. The inserts or side panels are then inserted into the Pi causing the adhesive to flow up into the gaps existing between the plate and the sides of the Pi. Here, the viscous adhesive is squeeze flowed to the surface aimed to bond, therefore the process is referred to Insertion Squeeze Flow (ISF) bonding process. The curing of the adhesive is done without additional external pressure or clamping forces at 65 °C during 1 hour. A bond is formed between the skin and the insert/ plate when the adhesive is set. In order to secure the tolerances of the bonding thickness, carbon pin rods were used at the end or along the Pi or semi-Pi profile.

Figure 11: Assembly equipment based on Pneumatic press principle

The concept developed shows that automatic bonding application is possible by means of a simple pneumatic principle. The positioning of the inserts as well as the Pi, in this case, can be easily achieved by means of physical spacers. Complete fixing of one part is also necessary while the other shall be available to glide. The spacers can also be used as guides, which together with carbon pin rods or other material assure the positioning of the insert in the Pi accurately. In order to avoid the flow of adhesive at the ends of the Pi-profile, simply a Teflon adapted taps or rubber sliding guides for more complicated geometries as depicted in figure 12 can be used. A non-negligible pressure is also required at this ends.

Figure 12: Rubber sliding guides to avoid adhesive flow at the end of the structure

In order to control and assure that the flow of the adhesive has reached the full surface on both sides of the Insert and the Pi-part, non destructive testing (NDT) analyses were carried out. The used NDT methods were X-ray and ultrasound C-scan. In order to evaluate the ratio of surface without and with adhesive the statistic function by C-scan was used.

Figure 13: X-ray and C-scan analysis of a bonded plate.

TESTING OF BONDED JOINTS

To test the sensitivity of the bonding process different gap sizes, adhesive viscosities and adhesive application methods were tested on a structure of lower level of complexity than the flap track. The joint element used in the evaluation of mechanical performances and fracture behaviour by adhesive lack was the double lap shear specimen illustrated in figure 14.

Figure 14: Illustration of the Double Lap Shear specimen

The bonded line thickness was tested with 3 different configurations, i.e. 0.5/0.5mm, 0.3/0.7mm and 0.1/0.9mm. The investigated surface treatments were grinding, low pressure plasma (LPP), grid blasting and atmospheric plasma (AP). Adhesive application was evaluated for thin layer pre-application and dipping (Pre) and Insertion Squeeze flow. Three different viscosities were investigated for both specimens. The variation on viscosity is achieved by mixing EA9395 and EA9396 with different ratios. Finally, two surface conditions were tested; with peel-ply and without.

Figure 15: Summary of most relevant DLS-Results

Where base define 0.5/0.5mm, LPP, ISF, 80% EA9395 and 20% EA9396 and with peel-ply curing. V100 means 100% EA9395 and V70 70% EA9395 and 30% EA9396. Finally SCT represent without Peel-ply. All parameters in figure 15 differ only in one from the base, as defined just above.

Taken into account all valid tests, all surface treatments improved the wetting of the bonded surfaces compared to untreated specimens. All methods for surface treatment deliver similar results. However, it is interesting to remark the lower scatter produced by grinding and grid blasting. Although there is a slightly improvement on shear strength due to misalignment, this is not recommended due to the difficulty to reach a completed adhesive distribution on both sides of the gap. This arises from capillarity effects. The variation of shear strength due to viscosity is nearly negligible for 100% and 70% of EA9396.

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